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The Future of Vocational Education and Training in Europe. Scenarios for 2035: A Symposium¹

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Abstract

Context: The main research question of the symposium is how the latest findings from scenario research impact theoretical research on vocational education and training, VET policies, and the evolution of VET systems in various countries.

Approach: The symposium includes four presentations followed by a discussion. One of the important expected outcomes of the symposium is that the new scenarios hold the potential to catalyse supporting future innovation and strategies in vocational education and training.

Findings/Conclusion: We propose that the regular application of the scenario approach could be a useful complement to various other prospective approaches used to guide European employment and vocational training policies.

Keywords: vocational education and training, scenarios, educational policy, economic aims, transformation

¹ The contributions are based on articles published in the thematic issue of ‘The future of VET’ of the Hungarian Educational Research Journal in 2022, edited by Jörg Markowitsch, Jens Bjornavold and Magdolna Benke.

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1 Introduction³

The symposium will draw on two sources. On the one hand, Cedefop's research 'The changing nature and role of VET in Europe (2015-18)', and, on the other hand, further research that has provided the background for the studies on the HERJ thematic issue on 'The future of VET' published in 2022, edited by Jörg Markowitsch, Jens Bjornavold and Magdolna Benke. Based on the findings of Cedefop's research project 'The changing nature and role of VET in Europe' (2015-18), our paper outlines the development and transformation of VET in Europe over the past two decades.

By examining change from an epistemological-pedagogical, institutional and socio-economic perspective, the paper will illustrate the stability and path dependency of national VET systems and how this circumstance maintains the overall diversity of VET in Europe. In addition, the paper will also outline how gradual changes and significant social and economic shocks are combined to change the orientation of VET. Mapping and analysing the past will help us to outline possible scenarios for the future of VET in Europe. Three main scenarios - pluralist, distinctive, and specialized vocational education and training - help to illustrate the different directions vocational education and training could take in the next two decades and the challenges and opportunities that each direction presents. The symposium will refer to theoretical works that are fundamental behind scenario research and to some 'extraneous' theoretical work that has been stimulated by scenario research.

The study of vocational education and training in the two participating countries (Switzerland and Hungary) presents an insight into various topics and challenges. It shows different approaches, research targets, and the organisation of dual training in Europe.

The scenario theme also provides an opportunity to draw attention to future issues that can only be approached by logical deduction.

It is hoped that the symposium and its associated publications will also be of great help in launching a series of meaningful debates on the questions left open by the research, both within the professional community of the symposium participants and within the professional community of the countries represented in the thematic volume of HERJ, and also among the readers of HERJ.

6 Conflicting Roles of Vocational Education: Civic, Industrial and Market Tensions before Connectivism and VET Scenarios.⁴

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6.1 Introduction

The economics of conventions is a theoretical approach which has been developed by French sociologists (Boltanski & Chiapello, 2002; Boltanski & Thévenot, 2006) and that has been applied in the field of education (Derouet, 1989; Derouet et al., 2015; Verdier, 2016) and vocational education and training (Bernad & Molpeceres 2010; Berner, 2017; Marhuenda, 2017; Marhuenda & Molpeceres, 2020; Martínez & Molpeceres, 2010; Zehnder & Gonon, 2017).

VET policies and practices are permanently subject to reform, promoted by national governments but also by international institutions, the European institutions playing a relevant role in fostering possible ways to improve the effectiveness of VET. All actors involved are

³ The Introduction is partly based on the following article: Markowitsch, J., & Bjornavold, J. (2022). Scenarios for Vocational Education and Training in Europe in the 21st century. *Hungarian Educational Research Journal*, <https://doi.org/10.1556/063.2021.00116>

⁴ This contribution is based on an article published in the *Hungarian Educational Research Journal* in 2022.

conscious of their relative position of power and claim their legitimation to point the direction that reforms may take. Different actors hold different rationales, and they have to confront each other in order to establish their discourse and to better negotiate with each other.

Insofar conventions are shared by those who use them but also recognised by those with whom they have to negotiate; they may prove useful for analysing the current proposal of different scenarios described by Cedefop (2020). Such a proposal can be subject to interpretation from the perspective of the economics of convention, allowing us to identify the mindsets used by different actors negotiating these, critique and compromise being the main forces behind such negotiations.

6.2 The Economics of Conventions

My first assumption is that the connectivist order, also known as the projective city, is the context in which Europe finds itself nowadays. If this is right, it sets the framework for all other conventions to adapt. This does not imply that the projective city is the only framework, but it proves particularly useful to understand today's VET systems, labour and economic relations.

A second assumption is that three of the conventions proposed by this French tradition have already proved useful in analysing VET developments in different European countries. These are the civic, industrial and market conventions that have enjoyed different weight and different power positions in several European countries throughout the history of their VET systems. The main aims pursued by these systems embed the notion of worth that vocational education has enjoyed as the result of the conflict over the power of the different actors involved.

By analysing the scenarios, I aim to see whether they represent a variety of justifications, and which are the ones that apply better than the rest. This is relevant insofar as the picture of the scenarios indicates that no country remains stable and that all of them are on the move. Furthermore, this move is in different directions, which is probably the result of the negotiations among the different countries involved.

6.3 Scenarios Seen from the Perspective of the Sociology of Conventions

Economic, social and demographic changes are valid explanations behind the reforms that different European countries want to take. Employer demands are always out of doubt as crucial dimensions to be addressed by any VET system, but sustainability has also become an intangible asset that no country wants to avoid. Mobility of workers, including migration, is another dimension that adds pressure on the reforms upon VET systems.

Among the axis used by Cedefop to allocate country patterns, some seem to be favouring the projective city, like pluralism, diversity of learning approaches, ambiguity and patchwork. In fact, the axis portrayed by Cedefop (2000, 69) to allocate country patterns consist of an invitation to assume the projective city as a ruling justification.

However, it seems that the connectivist convention is more likely to find agreements with the market than with the civic convention. Ambiguity is also better accepted by market approaches than by civic ones, which tend to favour equality above difference. Civic regulations are often associated with stability, and mobility is a more demanded value by connectivism, but also one welcomed by market conventions.

Connectivism, as an overwhelming convention, is ready to reach agreements with all other conventions, though it suits best the market one. The power of the market was already indicated by Derouet as an indication of the diminishing power of the civic convention that is still the one most appropriate for compulsory education. The implications this may have not only in terms of VET systems but also in larger terms of political engagement of the European population, increasing populism and nationalism is relevant. The European Union's claim to be the most

cohesive society and the most representative of human rights is however a sign of hope for civic conventions to find its way also through VET reforms.

6.4 Conclusions

The projective city may be able to overcome different historical traditions and their relations to transition and welfare regimes, and it may be an appropriate legitimation for the replacement of welfare by workfare. The European Deal is behind the VET scenarios proposed by Cedefop, and the cases of Switzerland and Hungary presented in this symposium illustrate different ways in which actors in those countries are addressing tensions and finding new balances.

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7 Methodological Choices in Developing Scenarios in Vocational Education and Training – Reflections on three European Scenario Projects⁵

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7.1 Introduction

Scientific attempts to support policy-making with a view to the future can quickly bring science into competition with science fiction. A compromise between science and science fiction in order to support decision-making in this respect is the so-called scenario method.

7.2 Analysing and Comparing Scenarios in VET

As a matter of fact, only three international scenario projects on VET have been carried out in the past 20 years. All of them were conducted by Cedefop, the European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training (see also Cedefop, 2020, pp. 192-197). We refer to them by the publication date of the studies as “Scenarios 2003”, “Scenarios 2010” and “Scenarios 2020” (Cedefop 2003, 2010, 2020). In a contribution that maps 50 years of experience with scenarios, van Notten et al. (2003) classify scenarios according to three questions: a) what is the goal of the respective project, b) what is its content and c) how is the process designed? In Table 1 we summarize key differences between the three scenario approaches according to these criteria.

Table 1
Mapping the three Cedefop Scenarios studies according to criteria from the scenario literature

	2003	2010	2020
Goals	Strategy formation, for VET in Europe and country level (p. 7)	Analytical tool for stakeholders, considering different aspects of the development of qualifications (p. 220)	Development of potential future paths, plausible and consistent pictures, supporting the European dialogue (p. 189, p. 197)
Timescale	Short-term (10 years)	Short-term (10 years)	Longer term (15-20 years)
Exploratory or decision support	Strong focus on decision support than exploration	Exploration and decision support	Exploration and decision support
Process design	Formal and intuitive elements Partly participatory on the national level	Mainly intuitive, mainly desk research	Mainly intuitive, desk research and participatory elements on the European level
Database	Sequence of quantitative and qualitative data analysis	Combination of quantitative and qualitative data and analysis	Combination of quantitative and qualitative data and analysis
Methods/instruments	European level trend survey Multiple national approaches including interviews and workshops	Integrated analysis of several studies of Cedefop on qualifications	28 country analysis of European trends and drivers in VET Case studies on selected countries; Europe level expert survey on trends in VET; European level scenario workshop <i>(continued on next page)</i>

⁵ This contribution is based on an article published in the Hungarian Educational Research Journal in 2022.

Content	4 contextual scenarios – country level scenarios	4 qualification system scenarios	3 basic and 6 detailed VET scenarios
Description, story	Snapshot	Snapshot	Chain, storytelling
Perspective/vantage point	Mainly prospective	Mainly prospective	Combining retrospective and prospective
Scenario dimensions	Socio-economic development/systemic divergence or convergence STEEP Model	Dynamics of the qualification system/supply-led or demand-driven	Relative position of VET within the education system/characterisation of VET

Note. Source: Authors

In Table 2 we show the results of our discussion around the following themes:

- What is the relationship between the scenarios, their context and what are the drivers of change?
- What role do future archetypes – a topic that is emphasized in the recent methodological scenario process - play in the regard to scenarios of VET
- We then bring the two discussions together and introduce the difference between transactional and contextual scenarios.

Table 2
Summary of the analysis

	2003	2010	2020
Type of scenario approach	Institution-based / Contextual	Issue-based	Institution-based/transactional
Scenario process	Formal, strongly structured	Mix of intuitive and formal approaches	Mix of intuitive and formal approaches
Result	Complex set of scenarios, 4 European meta scenarios and strategies	European qualification system scenarios	3 overarching European VET Scenarios and 6 detailed scenarios
Relation to archetypes	high	low	low
Perspective/vantage point	Mainly prospective	Mainly prospective	Combining retrospective and prospective
Description, story	multiple comprehensive snapshots on different levels	Snapshot	Developmental chain that can be related to external developments different ways
Use of the scenario	Testbed for strategies	-	Stand-alone stories that can be used as reference in strategic communication

Note. Source: Authors

7.3 Conclusions

A regular discussion in research, policy and practice taking into account the state of the art of discussion on scenarios of VET and general future scenarios would be worthwhile. This should also cover the continuous verification, review and reflection of past scenarios and foregone future studies on VET, including skills forecasts. It would fit very well with recent postulations of the Expert Group on Foresight Modelling (2015).

From our experiences, we can draw the following lessons for the further establishment of such a process: The discussion about recurring basic patterns of argumentation in future scenarios as well as the significance of generally existing ideas about the future present themselves as an interesting basis for the reflection of scenarios. However, they are too general for the VET

scenarios discussed here. Hence, the notion of scenario archetypes does not directly apply to the domain of VET.

Scenarios about VET can be classified as "institution-based" scenarios. With the claim to constructing international/European scenarios, the diversity of the different systems must also be taken into account. These two facts, the institutional focus and the diversity of conceptions on VET, are the reasons why the idea of archetypes or purely contextual scenarios seems to be limited to the field of VET. On the other hand, archetypes could be an excellent basis for placing the different VET scenarios in their broader societal context.

In light of existing research, we would argue for the role that the relative independent VET systems and practices can play in market and technological developments. In future studies of VET, results of skills and labour forecasts (that are usually looking at the "demand side") need to be balanced with research on changing skills governance, feedback mechanisms and changing VET policies that do justice to the structuring effect of the training system, something which has at least a long-term impact on the demand on the labour market.

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8 Past and future evolution of VET Systems as a combination of diverging aims. The Case of Swiss VET System.⁶

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Abstract

Context: The goal of this contribution is to propose a theoretical model to analyze the evolution of VET systems based on the notion of aim, hinting at a nearby future: in particular on the economic, social and educational aims that are commonly attributed to VET and whose content and interaction vary according to the countries and historical moments considered.

Approach: We adopt a discourse-analysis approach in order to bring out the aims attributed to VET from the public debates around this field. We focus our analysis on the development of the Swiss VET system from 1880 to 2030.

Findings: Three major aims characterize the evolution of the Swiss system: economic, social and educational purposes. The importance of these three aims varies according to the time. While the economic purpose remains important throughout the period studied, the social purpose varies according to the societal challenges that Switzerland has faced, while the educational purpose has seen its importance increase in recent decades.

Conclusion: The notion of aim lends itself well to describing the evolution of vocational training systems. The purposes attributed to VET change according to the country and the historical period, revealing specific weighting between the different purposes. The analysis of the

⁶ This contribution is based on an article published in the Hungarian Educational Research Journal in 2022.

evolution of aims is mainly based on a historical perspective, but it can also formulate future projections on the basis of current discourses on the future development of the field.

Keywords: vocational education and training, economic aims, social aims, educational aims, Swiss VET system

8.1 Introduction

Any future forecast is built on a reading of trends that characterise the present and that we assume will continue into the future. However, the identification of trends is inevitably an exercise in historical reconstruction insofar as changes become trends as soon as they present a continuity over several years. Thus: no future forecast without historical analysis.

This also applies to forecasts in complex areas such as vocational education and training. Formulating a forecast on future trends means reading the changes of the last decades in detail, detecting regularities and noting the possibilities of their reoccurrence.

Our approach would like to combine a look into the past with a look into the future, based on changes that are relevant to the aims of vocational education and training systems.

8.2 The aims of VET

Vocational and educational training (VET) systems serve multiple aims, which find their roots in socio-cultural and economic contexts and evolve according to the times.

Depending on the country or the period, these VET systems have been charged with responding to different and constantly evolving challenges. The responses to these challenges have determined concrete choices at the level of their public policies, their structures and their organisation. A close look at the different aims assumed by VET systems offers an interesting perspective for a better understanding of their development and their specificities.

The notion of purpose has already been studied by many authors without however presenting a theoretical model for the analysis of VET systems (cf. Billett 2011, Euler 2013, Cedefop 2017, 2020). By adopting an exploratory approach, we refer to the notion of aim in order to build a theoretical framework that facilitates international comparisons between VET systems as well as the description of their evolution from the past to the future.

The notion of aim that we are putting at the centre of our reflection identifies "comparable functions" in different systems and, at the same time "comparable issues" over a long period. Formulated differently, the notion of aim allows us to designate what Dubar et al. (2003) call "common problems"; problems, stakes, questions "with which all members and institutions would be confronted and which would have given rise, historically [and in the future], to different answers according to the diverse and contingent configuration of the actors involved (p. 61; cf. also Gally 2011).

In order to develop this theoretical framework, we will reduce the multiplicity of the aims assumed by the different systems to three general orders of aims: (1) economic policy aims, i.e. providing qualified labour for businesses and thus supporting economic growth; (2) social policy aims, i.e. helping individuals to integrate into the labour market and society and contribute to the reduction of social inequalities; (3) education policy aims, i.e. completing compulsory school education and opening up the possibility of pursuing learning and training at higher levels.

However, these three aims overlap in VET and furthermore raise problems of incompatibility of expectations, which in practice often are resolved by compromises. These compromises have evolved in historically different ways depending on the socio-economic conditions of the different countries.

8.3 The case of the evolution of the Swiss VET system

Using an analysis of the specific case of the Swiss VET system, our research makes it possible to reconstruct the evolution of the balance between these three aims and their internal evolution, from the past (1880 onwards) to the future (up to 2030).

The identification of the different aims will be based on a discourse analysis approach⁷ of different sources of the history and the current debate of VET in Switzerland. This approach focuses on the arguments and positions as they emerge from the discourses pronounced at a given moment on a specific theme. More precisely, we will first focus on the explicit formulations of aims as they may emerge in the arguments and positions of the various actors active in the public debates on VET (politicians, experts in the field, civil servants, journalists, etc.). These arguments and positions shape the public debate, influence VET policies and, at least in part, find a concrete realisation in measures and structures adopted in the institutional processes of each country. At the same time, these measures and structures can also be considered in the historical analysis as indicators or traces, that allow us to track back to arguments and positions developed in the public debate.

This analysis will enable us to show that the Swiss VET system was drafted in the 19th century to achieve economic aims but that they also gradually integrated social and educational aims that have become increasingly important in the last decades of the 20th century.

Finally, on the basis of the launched debate of the social partners, business associations and education policy on the "Vision 2030" of the Swiss VET, it will also be possible to forecast the future evolution of balancing and navigating between these three aims, probably keeping the economic dimension at the heart of the Swiss VET, but nevertheless increasing the importance to the educational aims, meanwhile reducing the role of the social aims.

8.4 Conclusion

The notion of aim lends itself well to describing the development of vocational training systems. The purposes attributed to VET change according to the country and the historical period, revealing specific compositions between the different aims. The analysis of the evolution of aims is mainly based on a historical perspective. Still, it can also formulate future projections on the basis of current discourses on the future development of the field.

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⁷ Discourse analysis in the sense of Landwehr 2009, Keller 2011.

9 The Evolution of Vocational Education and Training in Hungary 1989-2035⁸

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9.1 Introduction

The social and economic changes initiated at the turn of the 1990s had a great impact on the education systems of the former socialist countries. Based on a critical analysis of national literature, my contribution presents the increasing challenges faced by VET in Hungary by discussing the following issues: historical traditions, declining prestige, governance, the involvement of social partners, and the introduction of dual training. Furthermore, I discuss the relevance of recently published European VET scenarios (Cedefop, 2020) for Hungary.

9.2 Evaluation of government measures to solve challenges faced by VET

In Hungary, VET has rich *traditions* dating from the last century. The structure of the economy led to an industrial world in which apprenticeship training was customary. The sudden shift of the regime towards a market economy posed a huge challenge for VET and made it necessary to redefine its role in the new socio-economic conditions.

The *prestige of VET* in the light of enrolment data has long been a critical point of Hungarian VET. Within the framework of the market economy, it has deteriorated even more than before. The government introduced measures that seek to make VET more attractive to young people through various ‘facilitation measures’ such as reducing general education and the ‘simplified’ content and delivery conditions for VET (Horn 2014, Kunert 2016, Mártonfi 2019). Obviously, the government’s above facilitation attempts to raise the prestige of VET have failed, as enrolment figures for the last three decades show (compare Figures 1 and 2).

Figure 1

Number of students in post-elementary full-time education by type of school in Hungary (1990-2020)

Note. Source: Author based on data from the Central Statistical Office of Hungary

⁸ This contribution is based on an article (Benke, M., & Rachwał, T. (2022). The evolution of vocational education and training in Hungary and Poland 1989-2035. *Hungarian Educational Research Journal*, <https://doi.org/10.1556/063.2022.00061>) focusing on Hungary.

Figure 2

Percentage of students in vocational and general post-elementary schools in Hungary (1990-2020)

Note. Source: Author based on data from the Central Statistical Office of Hungary

Researchers have emphasised the danger of improving occupation-specific skills at the expense of general skills. In parallel, as Mártonfi (2019) pointed out, the ‘lower branch’ of secondary VET suffers from a permanent loss of popularity and is increasingly lagging behind in the competition.

VET *governance* at different levels constantly raises important questions, where the topic focuses on centralization and decentralisation. After 2010, centralisation and national-level policies, downsizing of the role of VET professionals, and restricting professional publicity have had a suppressing effect on the formation of VET policy, with professionalism pushed increasingly into the background (Györgyi, 2019).

While the purpose of secondary VET is changing in Europe (Cedefop, 2020; Vorpe, Bonoli and Gonon in this paper), economic goals are dominating VET to this day in Hungary. The implementation of tasks arising from ad hoc market requirements seems to appear as a given priority, even employers are only able to define their medium- and long-term training needs within very narrow limits. In the meantime, the educational and social goals of VET have almost completely disappeared.

The *social partners* do not seem to appear in substance in the policy-making process. In general, reconciliation of social interests with the enforcement of the principle of partnership is very underdeveloped in Hungary (Benke, 2019) which, by implication, also affects social groups with weak advocacy such as apprentices.

Since 2010 the aim of the government has been to make VET even more responsive to the needs of the economy and to further strengthen and increase *dual VET*. For this, the German dual model served as a reference. But policymakers did not take into account the characteristics and operating conditions of the economies, nor did they pay attention to the criticisms regarding the German dual training. Moreover, the ‘copy’ was not precise: Hungarian students participating in VET spend about two or three years less on general education subjects than their German counterparts (Fazekas et al 2020: 64-65).

According to data (Eurostat, 2021), under the latest VET law (2019), all Hungarian students who enrolled in upper secondary VET, enrolled in dual training as well, similarly to

Germany. However, this statistic is rather about a statutory possibility. In theory, all VET students are candidates for dual training, but some of them – for certain reasons – cannot access it.

There is a risk that nowadays dual training better serves the coordination of economic needs and training only in the case of large companies who mainly train pupils for themselves. Researchers worry that companies are only interested in retaining students who make (higher) profits (Mártonfi, 2019).

9.3 Conclusions

Instead of democratization and pluralization, flexibility and empowerment, in Hungary the government's response to declining interest in VET is to be rigid, concentrate power, and over-regulate. We have to emphasize that simplification, considering VET mostly from a short-term labour market perspective, forgetting its complexity as a system with several external factors, has weakened its prestige and compromised its quality, especially in the lower 'branch' of VET. Highly centralized governance and the lack of broader, social functions for VET do not require or allow for meaningful negotiations between VET actors. The maneuver, which is an essential condition for meaningful negotiations, is provided only in moderation in Hungary.

The emerging problems and challenges regarding VET are unlikely to be resolved within VET itself and, instead, will require a comprehensive approach, the revitalization of youth policy, and a stronger enforcement of social policy to ensure the interests of students.

As regards Hungary, in the current circumstances and in the near future, only conditions for two scenarios seem to be in place: 'Distinct VET', because of the strong dual character of training, and 'VET for special purposes', because of the large group of young people with special needs. In my opinion there is little chance that decision-makers will move towards the 'Pluralist model', also because there is a lack of professional and social pressure to move in this direction.

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10 Conclusion

By studying the conclusions of the contributions in this paper, we can discover important similarities between the very different approaches. Thinking about future tasks, it is obvious that the tasks have been mentioned (addressing tensions (Marhuenda-Fluixá); the analysis of the evolution of aims of VET (Vorpe, Bonoli & Gonon), which are the result of negotiations and conventions; wishing for regular discussion in research, policy, and practice (Grollmann & Markowitsch); pointing out that the manoeuvre of VET actors is provided only in moderate level (Benke), is all about the necessity of partnership and communication between actors.

It has been discovered that both in Switzerland (Vorpe, Bonoli & Gonon in this paper) and the Netherlands (Broek, 2022), one of the key elements in the development of VET is cooperation and striving for agreement, and consensus, based on broad interests are considered important values. However, democratic leeway for manoeuvre, which is an essential condition for meaningful negotiations between VET actors (Marhuenda-Fluixá), is provided only in moderation in Hungary, where highly centralised governance and the lack of broader social functions for VET do not require or allow for meaningful negotiations between VET actors (Benke).

Scenario research raises a number of questions for the future (Benke & Rachwał, 2022), like, can ‘Pluralist VET’ open up new perspectives for secondary VET in connection with the development of local societies and economies? We consider the potential of the new scenarios as a catalyst for innovations and strategies in VET (Markowitsch & Bjornavold, 2022), where greater consideration of non-economic and non-market aspects may create new avenues and purposes for VET concerning social innovation. We also propose that the regular application of the scenario approach could be a useful complement to various other prospective approaches used to guide European employment and vocational training policies (Grollmann & Markowitsch).

Finally, if we accept that the ultimate driving force which perpetuates the problems and the failures outlined around VET is an overly utilitarian economic approach that reinforces a zero-sum game, is insensitive to social inequalities, and does not take into account the values associated with disadvantage (Benke, 2021), it is an interesting question for the future, if and how the ‘capability approach’ (Sen, 1999) by putting the needs of people first could cooperate with ‘Pluralist VET’.

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